

ITN RAINBOW deliverable D4.1

Efficient Meta-modelling for the simulation of soft tissue deformations

A. Python interface between scikit-learn and FEniCS for efficient meta-modelling

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YouTube video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=doZEg6FEeh4>

Source code location: https://bitbucket.org/ehmikaeili/meta_models_brainshift

FEniCS: <https://fenicsproject.org/>

Scikit-learn: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/index.html>

1. Introduction

This program is written for predicting the position of brain tumour in brain surgery. In the surgery, as surgeon makes incision and opens the skull, the brain tumour relocates under new boundary conditions. Predicting the position of tumor under different incision sizes is invaluable data for surgeons, which can be predicted by constructing metamodells. In this program, we construct a meta-model with two parameters of Young modulus and incision radius. We employ FEM to calculate the sample points and then use Gaussian Process Regression technique to interpolate the space between them. From mechanical perspectives, we consider the brain media as hyperelastic and the tumor is presented by elasticity coefficients.

To run this program, it is required to install FEniCS software for FEM calculations and sklearn Python library for training purposes.

1.1. Installing FEniCS software with Docker

To install FEniCS software inside Docker containers, follow the steps below in Bash environment.

Step 1. Create a folder on host (e.g. \$HOME/Brain_Shift) for pulling FEniCS source code

```
export FENICS_SRC_DIR=$HOME/Brain_Shift
mkdir -p $FENICS_SRC_DIR
```

Step 2. Go inside the folder in host (Brain_Shift) and pull the FEniCS sources

```
cd $FENICS_SRC_DIR
for p in fiat instant dijitso ufl ffc dolfin mshr; do git clone git@bitbucket.org:fenics-project/$p.git; done
```

Step 3. Install “fenicsproject” script to create development container

```
curl -s https://get.fenicsproject.org | bash
```

Step 4. Pull the latest FEniCS stable image

```
fenicsproject pull stable
```

Step 5. Go inside the folder created in host (\$HOME/Brain_Shift) and create Docker container "BrainShift"

```
cd $FENICS_SRC_DIR  
fenicsproject create BrainShift stable
```

Step 6. Now you can start the FEniCS Docker container and build the FEniCS components

```
fenicsproject start BrainShift  
fenics-build
```

1.2. Meta-modeling algorithms in Brain Shift program

In case you are outside of BrainShift Docker container, go inside it using the following command in Bash.

```
fenicsproject start BrainShift
```

Now we are inside the BrainShift container which access all the content of folder \$HOME/Brain_Shift and by inserting the following command we install "sklearn" library inside this container.

```
pip3 install -U scikit-learn
```

2. Main parts of meta-model program

This program is comprised of 4 main classes and 1 main function written in Python language. The first class is *dataset_class* designed to save and manage generated data inside ".npy" format files. The produced data are

- 1- data_x.npy: to store meta-model parameters, i.e. Young modulus and incision radius
- 2- data_y.npy: to store results from Gaussian Process Regression interpolation

```
class dataset_class:
```

```

def __init__(self,FileName):
    self.FileName = FileName

def SaveData(self):
    np.save(self.FileName + '_x.npy', self.x)
    np.save(self.FileName + '_y.npy', self.y)
    np.save(self.FileName + '_scales_x.npy', self.y)

def ReadData(self):
    print('./'+self.FileName + '_x.npy')
    self.x = np.load(self.FileName + '_x.npy',allow_pickle=True)
    self.y = np.load(self.FileName + '_y.npy',allow_pickle=True)
    self.scales_x = np.load(self.FileName + '_scales_x.npy',allow_pickle=True)

def AppendData(self,x,y):
    self.x = np.hstack((self.x,x))
    self.y = np.hstack((self.y,y))
    self.SaveData()

```

The “sampler_class” class is responsible for producing our meta-model sample data and each sample point will be calculated by finite element method. The produced samples will be passed in class “IO_tumor” as inputs.

```

class sampler_class:

def __init__(self,IO,dataset):
    self.dataset = dataset
    self.IO = IO

def sample(self,type,N):

    if type == 'uniform':

        self.dataset.x = np.zeros((N,self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0]))

        for i in range(N):

            self.dataset.x[i,:] = np.random.uniform(0,1,self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0])
            x_scaled = np.copy(self.dataset.x[i,:])
            for j in range(self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0]):
                x_scaled[j] = self.dataset.x[i,j] * (self.dataset.scales_x[j,1]-self.dataset.scales_x[j,0]) + self.dataset.scales_x[j,0]

            y = np.asarray(IO.eval(x_scaled,self.dataset.scales_x)).T
            if i==0:
                self.dataset.y = y
            else:
                self.dataset.y = np.vstack((self.dataset.y,y))

```

“IO_tumor” is a class defined for managing inputs and outputs of FEM simulations. The inputs are the meta-model parameters, i.e. Young modulus and incision radius. The outputs are the tumor displacement components (centre of tumor).

```

class IO_tumor:

def __init__(self):
    # Requested outputs
    self.output_FEM = {'displacement_tumor_x': 0.0, 'displacement_tumor_y': 0.0, 'displacement_tumor_z': 0.0}

```

```

def eval( self , parameters, bounds):

    if parameters.shape[0]>0:
        self.elastic_modulus_brain = parameters[0]
        self.radius_incision = parameters[1]
        # Inputs from sample
        self.input_FEM = {'Elastic Modulus': parameters[0],'Incision Radius': parameters[1]}
        print(self.input_FEM)

        brain_shift( self )
        output = self.output_FEM
        print(output)

    return output.values()

```

Gaussian Process Regression interpolation is carried out by class “GPR_class”.

```

# non-parametric meta-model
class GPR_class:

    def __init__(self,x,y):

        self.x = x
        self.y = y

        self.gpr = np.ndarray((self.y.shape[1]),dtype=np.object)
        for i in range(self.y.shape[1]):

            dy = 0.
            Kernel = ConstantKernel() * RBF( length_scale = 0.1 , length_scale_bounds=[0.01 , 1] ) + WhiteKernel( noise_level=1.e-3 ,
            noise_level_bounds=[1.e-8 , 1.0] )

            self.gpr[i] = GaussianProcessRegressor(kernel=Kernel, alpha=dy ** 2, random_state=100, n_restarts_optimizer=10).fit(self.x,
            self.y[:,i])
            print( 'self.gpr[i].kernel_ : ', self.gpr[i].kernel_ )

    def eval(self,x_star):

        vals = np.zeros((self.y.shape[1],1))
        vals_std = np.zeros((self.y.shape[1],1))
        for i in range(self.y.shape[1]):
            vals[i], vals_std[i] = self.gpr[i].predict(x_star.reshape(1, -1),return's=True)
        return vals, vals_std

    def plot(self,NPoint,Output=0):

        if self.x.shape[1]==2:

            fig = plt.figure()
            xPlot = np.linspace(0,1, NPoint[0])
            yPlot = np.linspace(0,1, NPoint[1])
            X, Y = np.meshgrid(xPlot, yPlot)
            Z = np.copy(X)
            Z_plus = np.copy(X)
            Z_minus = np.copy(X)

            for i in range(X.shape[0]):
                for j in range(X.shape[1]):
                    vals, vals_std = self.eval(np.array([X[i,j],Y[i,j]]))
                    Z[i,j] = vals[Output]
                    Z_plus[i,j] = Z[i,j] + 1.96*vals_std[Output]

```

```
Z_minus[i,j] = Z[i,j] - 1.96*vals_std[Output]
```

```
ax = fig.gca(projection='3d')  
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z,color='black')  
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z_plus,color='red')  
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z_minus,color='blue')  
ax.scatter(self.x[:,0],self.x[:,1],self.y[:,Output],marker='o',c='black')  
plt.xlabel('x')  
plt.ylabel('y')  
plt.show()
```

Function “brain_shift” defined in Python file brain_shift.py is called to perform finite element method simulations using FEniCS platform.

3. Brain Shifting simulation results

To test the program, run the *run_brain_shift.py* file inside “BrainShift” container with the following command

```
python3 run_brain_shift.py
```

The mesh used for brain and the incision boundary are shown in Figures 1, 2 respectively. The displacement component u_z prediction at different time steps are shown in Figure 3. Then we show the final position of tumor over a cross section of brain in Figure 4. Furthermore, we present the corresponding Gaussian Process Regression interpolation of the samples in Figure 5.

Figure 1. Computational mesh

Figure 2. Incision boundary (red colour is the cut area and blue colour is the intact area of skull)

Figure 3. Displacement contour component u_z for brain under surgery at different times

Figure 4. The final position of Tumor (grey colour) after opening the skull

Figure 5. GPR curve with two parameters (scaled Young modulus over x axis and scaled incision radius over y axis), black curve is the regression curve, and blue and red curves are confidence interval curves

4. Python codes of the Brain Shift problem

run_brain_shift.py

```
# Finite Element Program by Pierre Kerfriden and Ehsan Mikaeili - Mines ParisTech and Cardiff University
from brain_shift import brain_shift

brain_shift()
```

brain_shift.py

```
# Finite Element Program by Pierre Kerfriden and Ehsan Mikaeili - Mines ParisTech and Cardiff University
# brain model by Remigiusz Kreczynski
# https://grabcad.com/library/brain-the-brain
from dolfin import *
```

```

import numpy as np
import os

class void_IO:
    def __init__(self):
        pass

def brain_shift( IO = void_IO ):

    # Optimization options for the form compiler
    parameters["form_compiler"]["cpp_optimize"] = True
    ffc_options = {"optimize": True, \
                  "eliminate_zeros": True, \
                  "precompute_basis_const": True, \
                  "precompute_ip_const": True}

    # Data
    E1 = 10.0
    if hasattr(IO, 'elastic_modulus_sphere'):
        E0 = pow(10, IO.input_FEM['Elastic Modulus'])
    else:
        E0 = 2.

    if hasattr(IO, 'radius_incision'):
        radius_incision = IO.input_FEM['Incision Radius']
    else:
        radius_incision = 1.

    if hasattr(IO, 'position_sphere_x'):
        center_x = IO.position_sphere_x
    else:
        center_x = 0.5
    if hasattr(IO, 'position_sphere_y'):
        center_y = IO.position_sphere_y
    else:
        center_y = 0.5
    if hasattr(IO, 'position_sphere_z'):
        center_z = IO.position_sphere_z
    else:
        center_z = 1.5
    center = Point(center_x,center_y,center_z)

    t0 = 100.
    t1 = 0.01

    radius = 0.5

    # Meshing
    os.system('dolfin-convert brain_finer.msh mesh.xml')
    mesh = Mesh("mesh.xml")
    n = FacetNormal(mesh)

    file_mesh = File("results/mesh.pvd")
    file_mesh << mesh

    V = VectorFunctionSpace(mesh, 'P', 1)
    W = FunctionSpace(mesh, 'P', 1)

    # Define boundary condition
    class incision_func(SubDomain):
        def inside(self, x, on_boundary):
            return on_boundary and ( (x[2] >= -0.25) and ( ((x[0]-center[0])**2+(x[1]-center[1])**2) < radius_incision**2 ) )

    incision = incision_func()

    boundary_marker = MeshFunction("size_t", mesh, mesh.topology().dim() - 1)
    boundary_marker.set_all(0)
    incision.mark(boundary_marker, 1)

```

```

file_boundary_marker = File("results/boundary_marker.pvd")
file_boundary_marker << boundary_marker

ds = Measure('ds', domain=mesh, subdomain_data=boundary_marker)

bcs = []

def sigmoid(x):
    return 1 / (1 + np.exp(-x))

class tumor(UserExpression):
    def eval(self, value, x):
        smoothing_length = 0.01 * radius
        distance = sqrt( pow(x[0]-center[0],2) + pow(x[1]-center[1],2) + pow(x[2]-center[2],2) ) - radius
        alpha = sigmoid( distance / smoothing_length )
        value[0] = 0. * alpha + 1. * (1-alpha)

class elasticity_field(UserExpression):
    def eval(self, value, x):
        smoothing_length = 0.1 * radius
        distance = sqrt( pow(x[0]-center[0],2) + pow(x[1]-center[1],2) + pow(x[2]-center[2],2) ) - radius
        alpha = sigmoid( distance / smoothing_length )
        value[0] = np.exp( np.log(E0) * alpha + np.log(E1) * (1-alpha) )

class surface_elasticity_field(UserExpression):
    def eval(self, value, x):
        smoothing_length = 0.25 * radius_incision
        distance = sqrt( pow(x[0]-center[0],2) + pow(x[1]-center[1],2) + pow(x[2]-2.5,2) ) - radius_incision
        alpha = sigmoid( distance / smoothing_length )
        value[0] = np.exp( np.log(t0) * alpha + np.log(t1) * (1-alpha) )

T = tumor(element=W.ufl_element())
tumor_interp = Function(W)
tumor_interp.interpolate(T)
tumor_interp.rename('tumor','tumor')
file_elasticity_coefficient = File("results/tumor.pvd")
file_elasticity_coefficient << tumor_interp

E = elasticity_field(element=W.ufl_element())
elasticity_field_interp = Function(W)
elasticity_field_interp.interpolate(E)
elasticity_field_interp.rename('elasticity_field','elasticity_field')
file_elasticity_coefficient = File("results/elasticity_coefficient.pvd")
file_elasticity_coefficient << elasticity_field_interp

k = surface_elasticity_field(element=W.ufl_element())
elasticity_field_interp = Function(W)
elasticity_field_interp.interpolate(k)
elasticity_field_interp.rename('elasticity_field','elasticity_field')
file_elasticity_coefficient = File("results/surface_elasticity_coefficient.pvd")
file_elasticity_coefficient << elasticity_field_interp

B = Expression(('0.0','0.0','-1.0*t'),t=0,degree=1) # Body force per unit volume
T = Constant((0., 0.0 , 0.)) # Traction force on the boundary

# Elasticity parameters
nu = 0.3
mu, lmbda = E/(2*(1 + nu)), E*nu/((1 + nu)*(1 - 2*nu))

v = TestFunction(V) # Test function
u = Function(V) # Displacement from previous iteration
du = TrialFunction(V) # Incremental displacement

# Kinematics
d = u.geometric_dimension()
I = Identity(d) # Identity tensor
F = I + grad(u) # Deformation gradient
C = F.T*F # Right Cauchy-Green tensor

```

```

# Invariants of deformation tensors
Ic = tr(C)
J = det(F)

# Stored strain energy density (compressible neo-Hookean model)
psi = (mu/2)*(Ic - 3) - mu*ln(J) + (lmbda/2)*(ln(J))**2

# Total potential energy
Pi = psi*dx - dot(B, u)*dx - dot(T, u)*ds + inner(k*u,u)*ds(0)

# Compute first variation of Pi (directional derivative about u in the direction of v)
F = derivative(Pi, u, v)

# Compute Jacobian of F
J = derivative(F, u, du)

# Solve variational problem
solve(F == 0, u, bcs, J=J, form_compiler_parameters=ffc_options)

file_displacement = File("results/displacement.pvd")
u.rename('displacement', 'displacement')
file_displacement << u

T=1
dt = 0.25
t = dt
time_step = 0

while t < T + DOLFIN_EPS:

    time_step += 1
    print("time_step", time_step)

    B.t = t

    # Solve variational problem
    solve(F == 0, u, bcs, J=J, form_compiler_parameters=ffc_options)

    u.rename('displacement', 'displacement')
    file_displacement << u

    t+=dt

class sensor_field(UserExpression):
    def eval(self, value, x):
        smoothing_length = 0.5
        center_sensor = center
        Num = pow(x[0]-center_sensor[0],2) + pow(x[1]-center_sensor[1],2) + pow(x[2]-center_sensor[2],2)
        normal_const = np.sqrt( pow( (2*np.pi) , 3) * pow( smoothing_length**2 , 3) )
        value[0] = 1./normal_const * np.exp( - 0.5* Num / pow(smoothing_length,2) )

sensor = sensor_field(element=W.ufl_element())
sensor_interp = Function(W)
sensor_interp.interpolate(sensor)
sensor_interp.rename('sensor', 'sensor')
file_sensor = File("results/sensor.pvd")
file_sensor << sensor_interp

sensor_disp_form = inner( u , sensor * Constant((1.0,0.0,0.0)) ) * dx
sensor_disp_x = assemble(sensor_disp_form)

sensor_disp_form = inner( u , sensor * Constant((0.0,0.0,1.0)) ) * dx
sensor_disp_z = assemble(sensor_disp_form)

sensor_disp_form = inner( u , sensor * Constant((0.0,1.0,0.0)) ) * dx
sensor_disp_y = assemble(sensor_disp_form)
print("sensor_disp_z", sensor_disp_z)

vol_sensor_form = sensor * dx(mesh)

```

```

vol_sensor = assemble(vol_sensor_form)
print("vol_sensor",vol_sensor)

print("sensor_disp_z/vol_sensor",sensor_disp_z/vol_sensor)

if hasattr(IO, 'output_FEM'):

    IO.output_FEM = {'displacement_tumor_x': sensor_disp_x/vol_sensor, 'displacement_tumor_y': sensor_disp_y/vol_sensor,
'displacement_tumor_z': sensor_disp_z/vol_sensor}
    else:
        print({'displacement_tumor_x': sensor_disp_x/vol_sensor, 'displacement_tumor_y': sensor_disp_y/vol_sensor,
'displacement_tumor_z': sensor_disp_z/vol_sensor})

```

meta_models.py

Meta-modelling program by Pierre Kerfriden and Ehsan Mikaeili - Mines ParisTech and Cardiff University

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D
import random
from scipy.optimize import fmin_bfgs, fmin
from sklearn.gaussian_process.kernels import ConstantKernel, RBF, WhiteKernel
from sklearn.gaussian_process import GaussianProcessRegressor
from brain_shift import brain_shift

class dataset_class:

    def __init__(self,FileName):
        self.FileName = FileName

    def SaveData(self):
        np.save(self.FileName + '_x.npy', self.x)
        np.save(self.FileName + '_y.npy', self.y)
        np.save(self.FileName + '_scales_x.npy', self.y)

    def ReadData(self):
        print('./'+self.FileName + '_x.npy')
        self.x = np.load(self.FileName + '_x.npy',allow_pickle=True)
        self.y = np.load(self.FileName + '_y.npy',allow_pickle=True)
        self.scales_x = np.load(self.FileName + '_scales_x.npy',allow_pickle=True)

    def AppendData(self,x,y):
        self.x = np.hstack((self.x,x))
        self.y = np.hstack((self.y,y))
        self.SaveData()

class sampler_class:

    def __init__(self,IO,dataset):
        self.dataset = dataset
        self.IO = IO

    def sample(self,type,N):

        if type == 'uniform':

            self.dataset.x = np.zeros((N,self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0]))

            for i in range(N):

                self.dataset.x[i,:] = np.random.uniform(0,1,self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0])
                x_scaled = np.copy(self.dataset.x[i,:])
                for j in range(self.dataset.scales_x.shape[0]):
                    x_scaled[j] = self.dataset.x[i,j] * (self.dataset.scales_x[j,1]-self.dataset.scales_x[j,0]) + self.dataset.scales_x[j,0]

            y = np.asarray(IO.eval(x_scaled,self.dataset.scales_x)).T
            if i==0:
                self.dataset.y = y
            else:

```

```

self.dataset.y = np.vstack((self.dataset.y,y))

class IO_tumor:

    def __init__(self):
        # Requested outputs
        self.output_FEM = {'displacement_tumor_x': 0.0, 'displacement_tumor_y': 0.0, 'displacement_tumor_z': 0.0}

    def eval( self , parameters, bounds):

        if parameters.shape[0]>0:
            self.elastic_modulus_brain = parameters[0]
            self.radius_incision = parameters[1]
            # Inputs from sample
            self.input_FEM = {'Elastic Modulus': parameters[0],'Incision Radius': parameters[1]}
            print(self.input_FEM)

            brain_shift( self )
            output = self.output_FEM
            print(output)

        return output.values()

# non-parametric meta-model
class GPR_class:

    def __init__(self,x,y):

        self.x = x
        self.y = y

        self.gpr = np.ndarray((self.y.shape[1]),dtype=np.object)
        for i in range(self.y.shape[1]):

            dy = 0.
            Kernel = ConstantKernel() * RBF( length_scale = 0.1 , length_scale_bounds=[0.01 , 1] ) + WhiteKernel( noise_level=1.e-3 ,
noise_level_bounds=[1.e-8 , 1.0] )

            self.gpr[i] = GaussianProcessRegressor(kernel=Kernel, alpha=dy ** 2, random_state=100, n_restarts_optimizer=10).fit(self.x,
self.y[:,i])
            print( 'self.gpr[i].kernel_ : ', self.gpr[i].kernel_ )

    def eval(self,x_star):

        vals = np.zeros((self.y.shape[1],1))
        vals_std = np.zeros((self.y.shape[1],1))
        for i in range(self.y.shape[1]):
            vals[i], vals_std[i] = self.gpr[i].predict(x_star.reshape(1, -1),return_s='True)
        return vals, vals_std

    def plot(self,NPoint,Output=0):

        if self.x.shape[1]==2:

            fig = plt.figure()
            xPlot = np.linspace(0,1, NPoint[0])
            yPlot = np.linspace(0,1, NPoint[1])
            X, Y = np.meshgrid(xPlot, yPlot)
            Z = np.copy(X)
            Z_plus = np.copy(X)
            Z_minus = np.copy(X)

            for i in range(X.shape[0]):
                for j in range(X.shape[1]):
                    vals, vals_std = self.eval(np.array([X[i,j],Y[i,j]]))
                    Z[i,j] = vals[Output]
                    Z_plus[i,j] = Z[i,j] + 1.96*vals_std[Output]
                    Z_minus[i,j] = Z[i,j] - 1.96*vals_std[Output]

```

```

ax = fig.gca(projection='3d')
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z,color='black')
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z_plus,color='red')
ax.plot_wireframe(X, Y, Z_minus,color='blue')
ax.scatter(self.x[:,0],self.x[:,1],self.y[:,Output],marker='o',c='black')
plt.xlabel('x')
plt.ylabel('y')
plt.show()

print('----- metamodeling demo by P Kerfriden and E Mikaeili -----')

generate_new_data = 0

dataset = dataset_class('data')
IO = IO_tumor()

if generate_new_data:
    dataset.scales_x = np.array([[0. , 1.0],[0.5 , 1.5]])
    sampler = sampler_class(IO, dataset)
    sampler.sample('uniform',N=30)
else:
    dataset.ReadData()

print('dataset.x',dataset.x)
print('dataset.y',dataset.y)

GPR = GPR_class(dataset.x,dataset.y)
GPR.plot([15,15],1)

```

B. Deep learning surrogate model for FEM solvers

Saurabh Deshpande, University of Luxembourg

Source code: https://gitlab.uni.lu/sdeshpande/deliverable_rainbow
SOFA Framework - <https://www.sofa-framework.org/download/>
Keras - <https://keras.io>

Description

Finite element method (FEM) is one of the most widely used tools for solving partial differential equations of boundary and initial value problems. Human tissue exhibits nonlinear deformation behaviour when applied with an external force, solving such non-linear equations using FEM is computationally expensive. In particular if this has to be done on consumers level hardware rather than a high-end parallel computer. One remedy to this problem is the use of model order reduction or domain decomposition techniques. Although the efficiency is compromised with the choice of a smaller basis set. Since a decade, machine learning has started to revolutionize several fields due to development of new algorithms and availability of more data every day. In this work we use a particular class of machine learning architecture called Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). We use the following CNN. This work has been inspired from Prof. Cotin's research on deep learning models for hyper-elastic materials.

U-NET CNN Architecture

We generate the synthetic training data of a cantilever beam deformation by using SOFA Framework. Simulation Open Framework Architecture (SOFA) is an open source framework primarily targeted at real-time physical simulation, with an emphasis on medical simulation. Each of the top surface nodes is applied with 100 random forces to generate the data. This data is trained using Keras library. Trained model is used to make new predictions, output the neural network is a displacement array consisting each dof of the cantilever beam.

Time of prediction using neural network approach is in the range of mili-seconds which makes it favourable to use. Following is visualization of one of the test sets, we compare the meshes of finite element solution. So the prediction of neural networks is stored in a .csv file and is imported in SOFA for visualization/comparison of Finite element and neural network meshes.

Force applied is $[-2.1941758, -1.45963101, -2.23671902]$ N

Max deformation using FEM -1.10 m

Max deformation using NN is -1.09 m

Avg error is 0.005 m

Max error is 0.035 m

Here I am showing another example comparing neural network and FEM mesh. As you can see time of prediction using deep learning model is very less compared to FEM time.

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